

WASTE MANAGEMENT ON CITY GURUGRAM, HARYANA

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Abstract

Gurugram – the ‘Millennium City’ has seen exponential development in terms of populace over the final few a long time due to business roads. Presently, as per the concern with Squander administration or squander transfer incorporates the forms and activities required to oversee squander from its initiation to its last transfer. This incorporates the collection, transport, treatment, and transfer of squander, alongside checking and direction of the squander administration prepare and waste-related laws, advances, and financial components. Squander can be strong, fluid, or gasses and each sort has diverse strategies of transfer and administration. Squander administration bargains with all sorts of squander, counting mechanical, organic, family, civil, natural, biomedical, radioactive squanders. In a few cases, squander can posture a threat to human wellbeing. Wellbeing issues are related with the whole handle of squander administration. Wellbeing issues can too emerge in a roundabout way or straightforwardly: straightforwardly through the dealing with of strong squander, and by implication through the utilization of water, soil, and nourishment. Squander is delivered by human movement, for illustration, the extraction and preparing of crude materials. Squander administration is planning to diminish the unfavorable impacts of squander on human wellbeing, the environment, planetary assets, and aesthetics. The cities as it were include two percent of the world’s arrive surface, however they are capable for expending over 75 rate of the planet’s assets and deliver 75 rate of the world’s squander. The foremost squeezing issue confronted by any urban middle in India nowadays is Metropolitan Strong Squander Administration (SWM). Quick urbanization and changing ways of life have driven to the era of gigantic sums of waste and squander within the urban zones. The present paper consider the Waste Management on City Gururam, Haryana, India with prime goals are- (i) To examine the Waste Management in the Gurugram City. (ii) To investigations the Remediation of Waste Management in Gurugram city. (iii) To discuss the Some Best Practices being adopted for Waste Management in Gurugram city. The technique of the inquire about could be a sort including an interpretative,

discussion, perception and consider auxiliary sources, like books, articles, diaries, proposal, college news, master supposition, and websites, etc.

Key Words: *Waste Management*

Introduction: The point of Waste Management is to decrease the perilous impacts of such squander on the environment and human wellbeing. An enormous portion of squander administration bargains with metropolitan strong squander, which is made by mechanical, commercial, and family activity. Proper administration of squander is critical for building maintainable and habitable cities, but it remains a challenge for numerous creating nations and cities. A report found that viable squander administration is moderately costly, ordinarily comprising 20%–50% of metropolitan budgets. Working this basic civil benefit requires coordinates frameworks that are effective, economical, and socially backed. A huge parcel of squander administration hones bargain with metropolitan strong squander (MSW) which is the bulk of the squander that is made by family, mechanical, and commercial action. Agreeing to the Interval Board on Climate Alter (IPCC), civil strong squander is anticipated to reach roughly 3.4 Gt by 2050; in any case, approaches and lawmaking can diminish the sum of squander delivered in several zones and cities of the world. Measures of squander administration incorporate measures for coordinates techno-economic instruments of a circular economy, compelling transfer offices, send out and moment control and ideal economical plan of items that are produced. Viable 'Waste Management' includes the practice of '7R' - 'R'efuse, 'R'educe', 'R'euse, 'R'epair, 'R'epurpose, 'R'ecycle and 'R'ecover. Among these '7R's, the to begin with two ('Refuse' and 'Reduce') relate to the non-creation of squander - by denying to purchase non-essential items and by decreasing utilization. The another two ('Reuse' and 'Repair') allude to expanding the usage of the existing item, with or without the substitution of certain parts of the item. 'Repurpose' and 'Recycle' include most extreme utilization of the materials used within the item, and 'Recover' is the slightest favoured and slightest proficient squander administration hone involving the recuperation of inserted energy within the squander fabric. For case, burning the squander to create warm (and power from warm). Certain non-biodegradable items are moreover dumped absent as 'Disposal', and this is often a "waste-'management'" practice.

Waste Management and Gurugram City: Show emergency of strong squander administration in Gurugram is the result of a long time of non-implementation of SWM Rules 2016. It is no astonish that we have been seeing rubbish heaped up all over the city & is being burnt as often as possible, exceptionally frequently within the near region of our private regions causing extreme discuss contamination & repeated wellbeing issues. The representation traces the concerns about the strong squander administration issues that Gurugram has been confronting for a few a long time on a day-to-day premise that seriously influence the quality of civic conditions within the city. Moment portion of the representation presents a way forward for feasible squander administration based on a Municipal Ward Asset Recuperation Policy. "To halt rehashing such emergency which has been happening nearly each year, we encourage MCG to enfirce entirely SWM Rules 2016 which orders to actualize source

isolation, in situ administration by Bulk Waste Generators(BWGs) by empanelling agencies, setting up MRFs at zone/ward level which can reduce quantity of waste (less than 15%) to landfill and maximize resources recovery,” said Shona Chatterjee, a resident and member of the volunteer team at Silver Oaks.

Present status of Waste Management in Gurugram City:

- Current Population of Gurugram – Around 18 lacs.
- Over 800 tonnes of waste is being generated in Gurugram everyday. On an average, around 30 % generated waste is biodegradable and the rest being non-biodegradable and inert in nature.
- Waste Segregation started in the city since September, 2015.
- Over Seven wards in Gurugram today segregate significant amount of waste at source and more are following the league.
- 2.5 % of the total generated waste is being segregated at present in the city. As we roll out the ambitious ‘Integrated solid waste management’ project in the city - by January 2018, we are sure to achieve 100 % source segregation.
- Door to door waste collection is taking place in all the 35 wards – 100 percent collection efficiency.
- Processing – 5 composting plants are run by MCG to convert wet waste to compost. Many other composting plants have been handed over to RWAs, which are being managed by the local community.
- Many private colonies and societies have adopted source segregation and composting as best practices.
- Disposal - At present, dry waste finds its way to the landfills, however very soon with the ‘Integrated solid waste management’ project, the dry waste will be used to generate power.

Processing and Disposal – Composting: The main composting methods implemented across the city are:

Existing legislation on Waste Management: Notification regarding user charges for Door to door collection of waste has been rolled out in Gurugram.

- Laws under approval – Bulk Garbage Generator and Spot Fine.
- As per the Municipal Corporation Act 1994, there is a provision of penalty for littering.
- Plastic below 50 microns has been banned in Haryana.

- Various IEC activities like Nukkad Nataks, banners, door to door awareness initiatives with partners like Feedback Foundation are being done.
- Social Media has been effectively used to generate awareness with the citizens.

Decentralized Waste Management:

- Gurugram has adopted Decentralized Waste Management through composting and other initiatives like involvement of rag pickers for further segregation of plastic and recyclable waste.
- Challenges faced in ensuring treatment at source - The dry and wet waste handling is in distant locations increasing the overhead cost and bringing down the efficiency.

Major Gaps and Challenges of Source Segregation:

- Limited awareness with citizens around the benefits of source segregation
- Citizen resistance towards user charges for door to door collection.

Some Best Practices being adopted for Waste Management in Gurugram city:

- Clear signs in the bin rooms and consistent wording, symbols and colors on all bins are being Ensured.
- Providing clean bins and bin rooms, that are free of dumped and undisposed waste since dirty and untidy waste facilities will demotivate visitors and staff to use the facilities.

Integrated Waste Management Process

- Closed-circuit television (CCTV) monitoring of waste rooms and bin storage areas.
- Leveraging students as change makers. Educating the students, teaching faculty and staff on importance of adequate waste management and sanitation facilities.

Remediation of Waste Management in Gurugram city:

- Proficient and shrewd squander administration is nowadays key to a dynamic city like Gurugram.

- The Civil Enterprise of Gurugram has begun an anti-encroachment and cleanliness drive in Sadar market to create it more pedestrian-friendly, taking after complaints of blockage and inappropriate sanitation.
- The organization has conveyed over 200 dustbins and conveyed 20 sanitation specialists to clean the paths. They have moreover constituted a extraordinary authorization group to evacuate infringements and take activity against violators.
- The Civil Enterprise of Gurugram (MCG) has begun an anti-encroachment and cleanliness drive in Sadar showcase, known to be one of the oldest and busiest markets of the city, to create it more pedestrian-friendly. The organization has too propelled a extraordinary campaign to guarantee legitimate sanitation within the advertise after getting a few complaints.
- Dispersed over 200 dustbins that have been kept exterior the shops and corners of each path.
- Made the courses of action for rubbish collection twice day by day, once at 11 am and once more at 8 pm. Over 20 sanitation specialists have been sent to clean the lanes.
- Encouraged businesspeople to keep the canisters exterior when the rubbish collection vehicle arrives. Incorporates collection, transportation, preparing and transfer of the strong squander together with setting up of squander to vitality control plant within the due course.
- Eco-green Vitality Pvt Ltd has been distinguished as the seller to roll out the strong squander administration project.

Grievance Redressal System:

- ✓ MCG Mobile App on Waste Management
- ✓ Swachh App on Waste Management
- ✓ Web Portal related Waste Management
- ✓ Call Centre for Waste Management
- ✓ MCG Social Media Channels for Waste Management
- ✓ CM Window for Waste Management

Grievance Redressal System through Mobile App

Haryana's First Integrated Solid Waste Management Project:

- Municipal Corporations of Gurugram and Faridabad signed MoU with Ecogreen Energy Pvt Ltd for the construction of Haryana's First Integrated Solid Waste Management Project
- Developed in accordance with all norms, regulations & directions by National Green Tribunal (NGT) and Solid Waste Management (SWM) Rules.

Solid Waste Management Project – Waste Collection Vehicles

- Includes collection, transportation, processing and disposal of the solid waste along with setting up of waste to energy power plant in the due course
- Ecogreen Energy Pvt Ltd has been identified as the vendor to roll out the solid waste management project.

Conclusion: Waste directly impacts the environment and its disposal pollutes the air, water and soil. Waste management reduces greenhouse gas emissions and improves the quality of air and water, and the condition of any area affected by the waste. India generates approximately 62 million tonnes of waste a year, and only 20% of this waste is recycled. The overproduction of waste is a major issue looming above the country, not just because of the distressing impact it has on society but also because about 87 lakh metric tonnes of this waste is hazardous in nature. Waste management refers to the activities conducted to manage waste from its collection to eventual disposal. Solid, liquid, hazardous, non-hazardous, household, industrial, biomedical, municipal, and organic waste are all a byproduct of industrial processes; waste management methods seek to reduce or eliminate the negative impacts that waste has on society.

Proper waste management is crucial for maintaining a clean and healthy environment in urban areas such as Gurgaon, a rapidly growing city in India with a population of over 1 million people.

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